

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF DEVELOPING FRUIT AND VEGETABLE CLUSTER IN OUR REPUBLIC

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ABSTRACT:

The article examines the importance of the fruit-vegetable cluster mechanism in increasing the competitiveness of our economy today. The opportunities and advantages provided by the cluster mechanism in the formation of a competitive economy are shown.

Our country's fruit and vegetable industry has great potential. According to statistics, the fruits and berries grown in our country in January-December 2022 on all farms are 2,983.5 thousand tons, or 104.5% compared to the corresponding period of 2021. But there is a problem in front of us, that we do not produce products that are competitive in the markets. The yield in orchards and vineyards is low. For example, in foreign countries, 70-100 tons are harvested from one hectare of intensive orchards, and up to 130 tons from some fruits. Therefore, the head of our state emphasized the need to establish a cluster system in fruit and vegetable growing. It was noted that the involvement of entrepreneurs with many years of experience in the field and the infrastructure of product storage and processing will have a good effect. Today, the sustainable development of agriculture directly depends on its competitiveness and modernization. Modernization, in turn, creates a promising competitive model of agriculture, strengthening cooperation with various economic entities operating in the processes of production, processing and sale of

agricultural products, its optimal social structure and requires agricultural entities to form organizational types compatible with market principles. In this direction, the establishment of agroclusters in Uzbekistan is an important factor. For this reason, it is important to study the theoretical and methodological aspects of agroclusters, which are considered a new institutional structure in the conditions of the republic, and the experience of foreign countries. The term cluster (translated from the English word "cluster") is a combination, collection of a number of similar elements, in the sense of a group, and an independent unit with certain characteristics. It was originally used in mathematics and, for the most part, in the natural sciences. In the 1970s, Swedish economists K. Fredriksson and L. Lindmark used this term to define the concentration of enterprises in a limited area. The term cluster as an economic category was introduced into the scientific process in the 80s of the 20th century by M. Porter. In his opinion, a cluster is a geographically inter-industry union of companies and institutions operating in a certain field. The essence of an agrocluster is based on A.A.Nastin: –an agrocluster is geographically located in one place, interdependent and mutually supporting each other in order to simultaneously and mutually cooperate to solve production tasks and unite in protecting the environment. It consists of a system of market entities consisting of various property owners - family farms, cooperative enterprises of farmers, social and scientific organizations, educational institutions and consulting services.

Using cluster methods based on the study of foreign farms is an alternative way for large farms. The cluster method in agriculture is an agrocluster, and an agrocluster is an entity that embodies the relations of the state, scientific research, processing, and business entities in accordance with the mutual market principles. Agroclusters are based on three characteristics, namely:

- regional specialization and localization of agricultural production;
- interactions between business entities of the network;
- the formation of technological interactions between various industries that produce finished products from agricultural products.

The center of the agrocluster is a group of agricultural producers, research and development institutions, various service infrastructure organizations, processing enterprises that unite the services of product sales, advertising and marketing on the basis of an agreement on strategic mutual cooperation. it can. Agrocluster is organized by mutual cooperation or

individual initiative of local government organizations (district administration), producers of agricultural goods (district farmers' council and farmers), processing enterprises. One of the important aspects of its organization is the high level of trust of its participants in each other through the implementation of cooperative projects that integrate the processes of agricultural products - production - processing - sale - research. The seasonal character of the production of fruit and vegetable products is, firstly, in carrying out the main technological processes, uneven distribution and consumption of economic resources, use of labor resources; secondly, in the preparation, transportation, storage and industrial processing of fruit and vegetable products; thirdly, in price formation in the market of fruit and vegetable products; fourthly, it is reflected in the organization of wages, finance and loans. Keeping the prices of agricultural products at the same level in the country in all seasons of the year, supporting the production of environmentally friendly products in all respects, providing preferential loans to agricultural producers, establishing food centers, regularly organizing cooperatives In order to protect the interests and rights of employees in the implementation of business, it is necessary to conduct trainings. Also, by recommending new varieties of agricultural crops, supporting business and various proposals of farmers aimed at reducing production costs and increasing the income of rural residents, providing various financial services and other mechanisms in line with the market principles of Uzbekistan It can be used by the Republican Council of Farmers to use the specific aspects of the conditions, to form non-governmental organizations of farmers at the republican and regional levels.

It is recognized in international literature that agricultural products are grown on family farms in the USA, Canada, Sweden, Denmark, and Japan. In Great Britain, France, Germany, Holland, Spain, Portugal, Denmark, farms operate cooperatively. In Finland, cooperatives are well developed and help to run farms. A small farming movement has been established in Poland and is based on narrow specialization. In Denmark, the activities of consulting centers are developed and they provide services to farms. 10% of the consulting service is financed by the state and 90% by the farm. Conclusions and suggestions The goal of forming clusters is to combine enterprises of the same industry located in the regions and educational, scientific, engineering, consulting, standardization, certification and other services in a single technological chain with them - on the basis of the organization of innovative

production of competitive goods. consists of directing creation. The establishment of agroclusters in Uzbekistan requires, first of all, the formation of the legal, organizational and economic foundations by the state. In this direction, first of all, the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the establishment of agroclusters" should be adopted. Secondly, to establish additional infrastructure facilities for agroclusters, i.e., agrotourism, hotel, thirdly, to monitor the study of agroclusters' activities, fourthly, to create a working group on the establishment of agroclusters in the republic and their tasks should be determined.

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